

INTONATION, SYNTAGMA AND RHYTHMIC GROUP IN THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article examines the general linguistic development of students, the instilling of skills in comparative analysis of linguistic units of diverse languages, in particular, Russian and Uzbek. The acquisition of correct pronunciation skills, correct stress setting are the most important tasks facing students. Thus, learning any language begins with mastering its sounds.*

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In both Russian and Uzbek languages, intonation (raising or lowering the tone when pronouncing certain parts of a sentence in the process of oral speech is widely used: to convey various shades of the meaning of a sentence.

In view of the very weak development of the issue of intonation in the Russian language and the complete lack of development of the issue of intonation in the Uzbek language, it seems possible for us to touch upon in this work only the differences in intonation between Russian and Uzbek interrogative sentences.

In Russian, a question can be conveyed with one intonation (raising the tone). The tone usually rises precisely on the word that is leading for a given question. For example:

1) Has everyone arrived today? (Did everyone come today? Or maybe someone didn't come?)

2) Has everyone arrived today? (Did everyone arrive today? Or maybe someone didn't arrive today?)

3) Has everyone arrived today? (Has everyone arrived today? Or maybe someone came on foot?)

In the Uzbek language, a question in similar cases is conveyed not so much by intonation as by a special indicator: question - interrogative particle, *mi*. It is she who gives the sentence an interrogative meaning (without any noticeable increase in tone). The leading word of the interrogative sentence is placed before the predicate, which is placed at the end of the sentence, and a stronger emphasis is placed on this leading word, accompanied by some relatively weak increase in tone.

The corresponding Russian interrogative sentences will be rendered in Uzbek as follows:

1) Bugun hamma keldimi?

2) Hamma bugun keldimi?

Moreover, even pronouncing all the words that make up a given sentence in the same tone, but with a stronger emphasis on one of the words, can completely convey the interrogative content of the sentence, since it contains a special indicator of the question - the particle *-mi*.

If a Russian interrogative sentence contains a special interrogative word (for example, interrogative pronouns *who? what?* or adverbs *where? where?*), the role of intonation is sharply reduced, since the question is still conveyed quite clearly by this interrogative word. The following

sentences can be pronounced with uniform intonation (without a noticeable increase in tone on any word), but with increased emphasis on the question word:

- 1) Who arrived today?
- 2) What did he say?
- 3) Where is my newspaper?
- 4) Why did the briefcase disappear?

A similar picture is observed in the Uzbek language. However, it is preferable to place the question word here at the end of the sentence (if there is a separately expressed predicate in the sentence, then before the predicate). Intonation can be even; the question word has a noticeably stronger emphasis. Thus, the above proposals will be expressed as follows:

- 1) Bugun kim keldi?
- 2) U nima dedi?
- 3) Gazetam qayerda?
- 4) Portfel qayerga yo'qolibdi?

In both languages, raising the tone on a question word is an additional phonetic indicator of the question, which also fulfills emotional tasks (greater interest in the subject of the question, greater excitement of the questioner, surprise, regret, excitement). Moreover, for each shade of emotion there is a special shade of intonation, stress strength, length of vowel sounds in words, etc.

When asking again in both languages, intonation (a sharp increase in tone of the word most interesting to the questioner) is the only means of conveying the interrogative content of the sentence.

In the Uzbek language, in these corpus particles *mi* to the leading word when asking again, it is not at all necessary. Most often, this particle is not added, since adding it reduces the meaning of asking again.

In Russian, if there are special interrogative particles in an interrogative sentence, sometimes the interrogative particle can be pronounced with a rising tone (Lena will go to the station today, huh?), but it can also be pronounced without raising the tone. (Are you going to the station? Or: Have you seen the teacher?). The situation is almost the same in the Uzbek language:

1. Sen ham borasanmi, a?
2. Karim keldi-ya?
3. Sen-chi?
4. Sening akang-chi?

Consequently, Uzbek students will somewhat underestimate the role of intonation when pronouncing Russian interrogative sentences that do not contain a question word. They will mistakenly put a question word at the end sentences before the predicate, that is, build a Russian sentence according to the Uzbek model. So, they might say:

- 1) Comrade Yuldashev when will he come today? instead of the usual for the Russian language: When will Comrade Yuldashev come today?
- 2) Where did you put my book? instead of: Where did you put my book?

Syntagma unites one or more words that represent some semantic and syntactic unity in a given sentence. Small sentences can also represent one syntagm. Phonetically, a syntagma is expressed by the fact that it is pronounced in a single "breath", without noticeable pauses between

words. Thus, a syntagma is separated from a syntagma by some pause (breathing space). We give an example of the supposed division of the Russian speech stream into syntagmas (syntagmas are separated by parallel vertical lines):

“We live in Western Siberia // Our region is famous for its mighty rivers: || Irtysh and Ob. || They flow from south to north. || And here || we once learned a wonderful thing || one Soviet engineer || suggested // about the possibility of turning the channels of Siberian rivers || towards Central Asia || in order for water || irrigated the Central Asian deserts || and turned them into a flourishing land.” ||

The same text in the Uzbek language is divided into syntagms as follows:

„Biz || G’arbiu Sibirda yashaymiz. || Bizning o’lkamiz || ulug’ daryolar bilan, || ya’ni || Irtysh va Ob daryolari bilan || Mashhurdir. || Bular || janubdan || shimolga qarab oqadi. | Mana endy // kunlardan bir kun // biz || ajoyib bir narsani eshitib qoldik || bir oddiy ingener || bu daryolarning suvi || O’rta Osiyo cho’llarini sug’orib, || bularni, || gullab turgan o’lkaga aylantirsin uchun, || Sibir dar’yolarini O’rta Osiyo tomoniga daratish mumkinliga haqida || o’z fikrini bayon qildi”. ||

From a comparison of these texts, it is clear that the division of the speech flow into syntagms in the Russian and Uzbek languages is not the same. In the Uzbek language, due to its syntactic features, there are invisible more syntagmas in the speech stream than in Russian. They do not always connect the same parts of the sentence that they combine in Russian. Thus, the Uzbek language is often characterized by a small pause after the subject, even in weakly common sentences, which is not the case in Russian.

In the Uzbek language, after the subject, secondary members are placed first, which seem to wedge themselves into the natural connection between the subject and the predicate, and in the Russian language, the predicate usually immediately follows the subject. Therefore, a pause between them occurs only when the subject is significantly burdened with definitions. The connection between the direct object and the control verb in Russian is generally closer than in Uzbek, where other parts of the sentence are often wedged between them.

The connections between definables and their noun definitions in both Russian and Uzbek languages are expressed from the point of view of interest to us in the same way, that is, definitions and defined, as a rule, are combined into one syntagma.

A more detailed study of both languages in this regard is possible only on the basis of a comparison of their syntactic structure in all its details. This can be done in the syntax section, noting the syntagmas characteristic of each language in the phonetic design of the syntactic constructions being studied in a continuous stream of speech.

In any case, taking into account the differences that are revealed even with the most preliminary analysis of the methods of breaking down speech flow into syntagms in the Russian and Uzbek languages, it can be assumed that in the Russian speech of Uzbek students these differences will somehow be reflected, giving rise to some typical errors, the elimination of which the teacher will have to pay attention to in the process of teaching Russian to Uzbek schoolchildren.

A rhythmic group is a word or phrase (within a sentence or syntagm) that phonetically stands out from adjacent words or phrases in that it is united in pronunciation by a stronger emphasis on one of the syllables of a given rhythmic group.

The division of the Uzbek speech flow into rhythmic groups is apparently more fragmented than the Russian one. In the Russian language, a stronger emphasis is again placed on the close association of the subject-pronoun and the predicate-verb into one rhythmic group, when they

follow one after the other and are each expressed in one word. Both languages are characterized by the inclusion of function words in the same rhythmic group with the meaning word. Nevertheless, in a number of moments the division of speech into rhythmic groups in both languages coincides (for example, combining the definition with the defined into one rhythmic group).

A more detailed comparison of the laws of distribution of a continuous speech flow into rhythmic groups in the Russian and Uzbek languages and an analysis of the duration of pauses between rhythmic groups and syntagms, a study of the dependence of the stress force in the syllables of a rhythmic group on the stress force in the main (unifying) syllable, analysis of the duration of vowels in rhythmic groups and reduction phenomena developing within rhythmic groups, all this has not yet been studied in both the Russian and Uzbek languages. Only after sufficient development of the listed issues in both languages will it be possible to compare them.

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